

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL 3

LECTURE NOTES – EDUCATIONAL INTERVENTION

WHAT IS HEALTH?

- According to the World Health Organization, health is defined as “a state of complete physical, social and mental well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity”.
- Good health is more important than being free from disease. Healthy people are more efficient, productive and live longer than unfit people.

WHAT IS HEALTHY LIFESTYLE?

- A healthy lifestyle can help you thrive as you move through your life's journey. Making healthy choices isn't always easy – it can be hard to find the time and energy to exercise regularly or prepare healthy meals. However, your efforts will pay off in many ways, and for the rest of your life.

STEPS OF HEALTHY LIFESTYLE MAINTENANCE:

- Be physically active for 30 minutes most days of the week. Break this up into three 10-minute sessions when pressed for time. Healthy movement may include walking, sports, dancing, yoga or running.
- Eat a well-balanced, low-fat diet with lots of fruits, vegetables, and whole grains. Choose a diet that's low in saturated fat and cholesterol, and moderate in sugar, salt and total fat.
- Maintain good personal hygiene.
- Proper sleep schedule of at least 7 to 8 hours a day.
- Stay out of the sun.

WHAT IS NUTRITION?

- Nutrition is defined as the science of foods, nutrients and other substances they contain; and of their actions within the body including ingestion, digestion, absorption, metabolism and excretion. While this summarizes the physiological dimensions, nutrition has social, psychological and economic dimensions too.

WHAT ARE NUTRIENTS?

- Nutrients are the constituents in food that must be supplied to the body in suitable amount.
- These include **carbohydrates, proteins, fats, minerals, vitamins, water** and **fiber**. We need a wide range of nutrients to keep ourselves healthy. Most foods contain more than one nutrient such as milk has proteins, fats, etc.
- Nutrients can be classified as macronutrients and micronutrients on the basis of the required quantity to be consumed by us every day.

1. CARBOHYDRATES:

- Carbohydrates, or carbs, are sugar molecules. Along with proteins and fats, carbohydrates are one of three main nutrients found in foods and drinks. Your body breaks down carbohydrates into glucose. Glucose, or blood sugar, is the main source of energy for your body's cells, tissues, and organs.

2. FATS:

- Fats are a type of nutrient that you get from your diet. It is essential to eat some fats, though it is also harmful to eat too much. The fats you eat give your body energy that it needs to work properly. During exercise, your body uses calories from carbohydrates you have eaten.

3. PROTEINS:

- Proteins are large, complex molecules that play many critical roles in the body. They do most of the work in cells and are required for the structure, function, and regulation of the body's tissues and organs.

4. VITAMINS:

- A **vitamin** is an organic molecule (or a set of closely related molecules called as vitamers) that are essential to an organism in small quantities for proper metabolic function. Essential nutrients cannot be synthesized in the organism in sufficient quantities for survival, and therefore must be obtained through the diet. There are two types of vitamins:
 - Water-Soluble
 - Fat-Soluble

5. MINERALS:

- Minerals in food are the elements present in food that are required by our body to develop and function properly. We can deduce that minerals are inorganic substances required by the human body to function correctly. The human body requires varying amounts of minerals daily in order to build strong bones and muscles. It also helps to maintain various bodily functions. For example, we need more calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, sodium, potassium and chloride than we do iron, zinc, iodine, selenium and copper.

6. FIBER:

- Fiber, also known as roughage, is the part of plant-based foods (grains, fruits, vegetables, nuts, and beans) that the body can't break down. It passes through the body undigested, keeping your digestive system clean and healthy, easing bowel movements, and flushing cholesterol and harmful carcinogens out of the body.

7. WATER:

- Water is an inorganic compound with the chemical formula H_2O . It is a transparent, tasteless, odorless, and nearly colorless chemical substance, and it is the main constituent of Earth's hydrosphere and the fluids of all known living organisms. Everyone should drink at least 2.5 to 3 liters of water each day.

	0-6 mo	1-3 years	4-8 years	Males 9-13	Females 9-13
Protein (g/day)	9.1	13	19	34	34
Carbohydrates (g/day)	60*	130	130	130	130
Fat (g/d--AI)	31*	ND	ND	ND	ND
Fiber g/d	ND	19*	25	31	26
Vitamin D (µg/d)	5*	5*	5*	5*	5*
Vitamin B12 (mg/d)	0.4*	0.9	1.2	1.8	1.8
Folate (µg/d)	65*	150	200	300	300
Calcium (mg/d)	210*	500*	800*	1300*	1300*
Iron (mg/d)	0.27*	7	10	8	8

From [Food and Nutrition Board](#), The Institute of Medicine, National Academies of Sciences ND: Not determined
* : AI - Adequate Intake
Bold: RDA - Recommended Daily Allowance

Figure Annexure 4(a): Recommended Daily Allowance of different nutrients by the body.

BALANCED DIET:

- A balanced diet is one which includes a variety of foods in adequate amounts and correct proportions to meet the day’s requirements of all essential nutrients such as proteins, carbohydrates, fats, vitamins, minerals, water, and fiber.
- Such a diet helps to promote and preserve good health and also provides a safety margin or reserve of nutrients to withstand short durations of deprivation when they are not supplied by the diet.

WHAT IS HEALTHY EATING?

- Healthy eating means eating a variety of foods that give you the nutrients you need to maintain your health, feel good, and have energy. These nutrients include protein, carbohydrates, fat, water, vitamins, and minerals.

- Eating healthy means following a healthy eating pattern that includes a variety of nutritious foods and drinks. It also means getting the number of calories that's right for you (not eating too much or too little).

Figure Annexure 4(b): Some Healthy eating habits for children.

IMPORTANCE OF HEALTHY EATING:

- Keeps skin, teeth, and eyes healthy;
- Supports muscles;
- Helps achieve and maintain a healthy weight;
- Strengthens bones;
- Supports brain development;
- Supports healthy growth;
- Boosts immunity; and
- Helps the digestive system function.